

Defense of Icon Veneration by John of Damascus

By Marina Toumpouri, Centre for Medieval Arts and Rituals, University of Cyprus

Entry tags: Text, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Byzantine text, Religious Group, Orthodox Christianity, Christian Traditions, Orthodoxy

The three treatises on the holy icons by St. John of Damascus were written during the first phase of the iconoclastic conflict, between the years 726 and 730-731 CE, on the occasion of the uproar caused in Byzantium after the issue of a decree by the emperor Leo III the Isaurian, which forbade the faithful to kneel in front of the holy icons and ordered that the icons should be hanged higher, so that it would not be possible to worship them. Despite the careful wording of the first decrees issued by emperor Leo, the rage of the iconoclasts against the holy icons did not take long to show its true face, as they were also opposed to the veneration of the Virgin Mary and the relics of the saints. Thus, iconoclasm took on explosive proportions and afflicted Byzantium and the Orthodox Church for more than 110 years. Among the reactions provoked by emperor Leo's measures against the holy icons were the intense theological debates, in which John of Damascus took part. John was a monk, priest, hymnographer, and apologist. He was born and raised in Damascus circa 675 to a prominent Damascene Christian Arab family. His father, Sarjun ibn Mansur, served as an official of the early Umayyad Caliphate. John was a savant, whose fields of interest and contribution included law, theology, philosophy, and music. He became a priest and monk at Mar Saba monastery near Jerusalem and undertook a spirited defence of the holy images in three separate treatises. The earliest among these works is his "Apologetic Treatises against those Decrying the Holy Images". The purpose of this first treatise was not to defeat the rival iconoclasts, but to offer a helping hand to the truth. However, because the content of his treatise was not properly understood, John was motivated to write a second treatise shortly following a second decree issued by emperor Leo. John wrote a third treatise in late 730 or early 731, where he attempted a more systematic account of the teaching on the holy icons, the veneration of the Virgin Mary, the saints and the holy relics. According to Damascene, the iconoclastic notions that the miracles, passions and achievements of Christ and the saints are not allowed to be depicted, is nothing but an evil inspiration, as are all heresies. In the case of the holy icons, the devil envies man because, by honouring the holy icons he can see the image of Christ and be sanctified through Him. According to Damascene, the purpose for which the holy icons are made is to reveal and show things that refer to the invisible reality, for which direct and complete knowledge cannot be otherwise accessed. This is considered an aid for one's spiritual benefit and, ultimately, salvation. The concept of "holy icon" includes inter alia the following types: the "physical" image because the physical existence comes first and then the imitation follows. More specifically, and as far as the holy icons are concerned, the first natural and unchanging image of the invisible God is his Son, Jesus Christ, who revealed the Father through himself. Another kind of image is man, who was created in the image and likeness of God. In addition, there is the painted image, which represents shapes, forms and types of the invisible and incorporeal in a perceptible way, in order to obtain a vague idea of God and the angels, since it is impossible to perceive and understand the incorporeal without figures. There are also the icons that represent religious events, miracles or virtues in order to be preserved in the memory of the faithful and as a glorification for those who excelled in virtue. Damascene concludes that we worship only God creator, for the veneration given to the icon passes over to its prototype. Decades after John Damascene's death, presumably at Mar Saba monastery on 4 December 749, his writings would play an important role during the Second Council of Nicaea (787), which was convened in order to settle the icon dispute.

Date Range: 726 CE - 730 CE

Region: Damascus

Region tags: Asia, Syria, Byzantium

Damascus, birthplace of John of Damascus.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Marina Toumpouri, "John of Damascus (675 – ca. 749-754) and the Defense of Icon Veneration" in F. Curta and A. Holt (eds), *Great Events in Religion: An Encyclopedia of Pivotal Events in Religious History*, vol. 2, Clio, 2017, pp. 370-372
- Source 2: Andrew Louth, "St John Damascene : Tradition and Originality in Byzantine Theology" Oxford University Press, Oxford 2002
- Source 3: Andrew Louth (trans.), "St. John of Damascus: Three Treatises on the Divine Images", St. Vladimir's Seminar Press, Crestwood NY, 2003

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://sourcebooks.fordham.edu/source/icono-cncl754.asp>
- Source 1 Description: Iconoclastic Council, 754
- Source 2 URL: https://www.catholic.org/saints/saint.php?saint_id=66
- Source 2 Description: St. John of Damascus

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://sourcebooks.fordham.edu/source/johndam-icons.asp>
- Source 1 Description: John of Damascus: In Defense of Icons
- Source 2 URL: <https://gutenberg.org/ebooks/49917>
- Source 2 Description: St John Damascene on Holy Images
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/authors/search/?query=John+of+Damascus,+Saint>
- Source 3 Description: John of Damascus

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked
– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper
– Specify: parchment

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: Quite the contrary. John of Damascus had angered the Emperor Leo so much that this latter

reacted fiercely to his treatise. Since he was unable to reach John physically, since John was in Saracen territory, Leo forged a letter purporting to have been written by John to him, informing Leo about the weak state of the defense in the city of Damascus and begging the Emperor to come and liberate the city from the Saracens. The letter was forwarded to the caliph, who summoned John before him, judged him guilty and ordered that his right hand be severed at the wrist. The sentence was executed but through the intervention of the Virgin Mary the amputated hand was miraculously restored. Moreover, John was condemned at the Iconoclast Council at Hiereia in 754, summoned by the Emperor Constantine.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: However, John's iconophile arguments in his three treatises were used to justify the production of religious images.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– Yes

↳ How are the volumes ordered?

–Specify: Chronologically

Notes: They are three treatises in defense of the holy icons. The first was written when Emperor Leo III issued his first edicts against the holy icons, between the years 726-727. Shortly after, Damascene wrote the second treatise, which is explanatory of the first, because there were some people who failed to understand its content. Finally, the third treatise, written about four years later (late 730-early 731), contains a more systematic account of the teaching on the holy icons.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Christian apologetics.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Bibliography

Notes: A short of bibliography citing former patristic texts. The author, in fact, in order to justify his views on the worship of icons, he not only does he cites Patristic texts written by prominent Church Fathers, but he also includes extensive verbatim parts in his own text.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: God is invisible, incorporeal, shapeless, can not be described or understood through the senses.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: John of Damascus follows the patristic tradition on God's omnipotence and omnipresence, according to which God is omniscient, knows everything before it is even created, since he is the one who created and sustains everything.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - I don't know
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - No
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No

Notes: Definitely not. The author refers to the prohibitions of the Old Testament and the commandments, which explicitly mention the prohibition of the worship of any

other (false) god, except the true God of the Patriarchs and the Prophets.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

↳ In dreams

– No

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: Since the text refers to the veneration of the holy icons, it is suggested that through that veneration a kind of communication is established.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Field doesn't know

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: As "human spirits" can be regarded the the great figures of the Christian tradition, namely the Apostles, the Fathers of the Church, the saints. Such spirits are cannot be considered as agents that interfere with people's lives by carrying out God's commands. They operate more as symbols and as examples for right Christian life, examples that every Christian has at his disposal, in this case through the holy icons, in order to get courage and inspiration to govern his life in a Christian way.

Furthermore, these figures are constantly used to confirm the views of Damascene. In other words, his reference to tradition, to the figures of the saints and Fathers of the Church, operates as a vindication for the author, providing to his text authority and legitimacy, being part of a uniform and indivisible tradition.

- ↳ Human spirits can be seen
– No
- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt
– No
- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world
– No
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– No
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– No
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living
– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings mentioned in the text are the angels and the devil. Specifically for this latter, the author mentions that he was the one who enticed people not to worship images, as honor and worship can harm him. Because the honor and worship of the icons refer to the original, that is, God and the saints, man receives sanctification, therefore he opposes the work of the devil.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: No other categories of beings are present in the text.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– No

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– No

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: Fidelity in the tradition of the Church.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Yes

Notes: The opposite. The text requires marginalization of those who do not belong to the group of iconophiles, i.e. the iconoclasts.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: The iconophile party, which eventually used John's three treatises at the Second Council of Nicaea or the Seventh Ecumenical Council (787).

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The iconophile party.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The text was never destroyed, even though John's writings angered greatly the Emperor Leo III.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Notes: The text is addressed to the whole congregation, that is both clergy and laymen, trying to clarify the correct faith, always according to tradition, for the honor and worship of the icons. In this light, the text was available both for formal teaching and for the enlightenment of the faithful on this subject.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Léonide Ouspensky , Vladimir Losskij Nikolaevič. The Meaning of Icons. Crestwood NY: St. Vladimir's Seminar Press. isbn: 0-913836-99-0.

Reference: Moshe Barasch. Icon: Studies in the History of an Idea. New York;London: New York University

Press. isbn: 0-8147-1172-3.

Reference: Andrew Louth. St. John of Damascus: Three Treatises on the Divine Images. Crestwood NY: St. Vladimir's Seminar Press. isbn: 0-88141-245-7.

Reference: Andrew Louth. St John Damascene : Tradition and Originality in Byzantine Theology. Oxford: Oxford University Press. isbn: 9780199252381.

Reference: Marina Toumpouri. John of Damascus (675 – ca. 749-754) and the Defense of Icon Veneration. (Florin Curta , Andrew Holt, Ed.), Great Events in Religion: An Encyclopedia of Pivotal Events in Religious History. Santa Barbara, CA: ABC-CLIO. isbn: 978-1-61069-565-7.

Reference: John Wortley. Iconoclasm and Leipsanoclasm: Leo III, Constantine V and the Relics.

Reference: Theodore Sideris. The Theological Position of the Iconophiles during the Iconoclastic Controversy.

Reference: Gerhard Ladner. Origin and Significance of the Byzantine Iconoclastic Controversy. Rome: Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies.

Reference: Leslie Barnard. The Graeco-Roman and Oriental Background of the Iconoclastic controversy. Leiden: Brill.

Reference: Dmitry Biriukov. HIERARCHIES OF BEINGS IN THE PATRISTIC THOUGHT: MAXIMUS THE CONFESSOR, JOHN OF DAMASCUS, AND THE PALAMITES.. *Scrinium*, 10(1) doi: doi:10.1163/18177565-90000102.

Reference: Dimitrios Pallis. A CRITICAL PRESENTATION OF THE ICONOLOGY OF ST. JOHN OF DAMASCUS IN THE CONTEXT OF THE BYZANTINE ICONOCLASTIC CONTROVERSIES. *The Heythrop Journal*, 56(2) doi: doi:10.1111/heyj.12212.

Reference: Michael Rhodes Craig. HANDMADE: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF JOHN OF DAMASCUS'S REASONING FOR MAKING ICONS. *The Heythrop Journal*, 51(1) doi: doi:10.1111/j.1468-2265.2009.00549.x.

Reference: Troy Speegle David. The Life and Theology of Images of Saint John of Damascus. Arlington: University of Texas.

Reference: Vassa Kontouma. John of Damascus: New Studies on His Life and Works. Farnham: Ashgate Variorum. isbn: 9781409446378.

Reference: Leonid Ouspensky. The Theology of the Icon in the Orthodox Church. (Jane de Vyver Horka), The Meaning and Content of the Icon. Paris: Editions de l'Exarchat Patriarcal Russe en Europe Occidentale.

Reference: Ambrosios Giakalis. Images of the Divine: The Theology of Icons at the Seventh Ecumenical Council, revised edition. Leiden: Brill. isbn: 978-9004099463.